

Innovative concepts and technologies for ecologically sustainable nutrient management in agriculture aiming to prevent, mitigate and eliminate pollution in soils, water, and air

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DELIVERABLE 1.2

PLAN FOR THE DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION AND COMMUNICATION

RELEASE 2

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Abbreviations

PDEC	Plan for the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
P1	During the project and 1 year after its end
DoA	Description of Action
P2	The next 5 years
SHG	Stakeholder Group
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The **ECONUTRI Deliverable 1.2**, the second version of the “Plan for the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication” (PDEC), outlines the update of the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) activities that have been undertaken by the consortium as part of WP1. The PDEC aims to maximize the impact of the project and includes all the material used in the D1.1 with additions to dissemination and communication activities, an analysis of the social media platforms, a preliminary detailed business plan, and a follow-up plan to foster the exploitation and uptake of all results.

All partners are committed to actively participate in dissemination, communication, and exploitation actions under the coordination of the WP1 leader CETRI. The DEC activities in China are coordinated by SPI, which possesses offices and a robust network in China, with the full engagement of all Chinese partners.

All partners in the consortium are implementing awareness campaigns in their respective countries and networks, contribute news and updates to the web portal and newsletter, and help keep the project's social media accounts active. The website has been translated into 10 languages, encompassing those spoken by all project partners. The WP1 leader (CETRI) is responsible for developing all the communication tools, with the aim of raising visibility and awareness of the project and its objectives.

This deliverable outlines the dissemination and communication strategy of the ECONUTRI consortium and aims to serve as a strategic document which partners will refer to, in order to implement successfully their individual and joint DEC activities. All the dissemination activities that have taken place so far, along with some potential future events are outlined in the second version of the PDEC

The ECONUTRI project has completed its 18-month period. Any aspects of the PDEC that will require refinement will be included in the final version planned for the end of the project at month 42.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The aim of ECONUTRI is to optimize and validate at commercial level nutrient management technologies that minimize or even eliminate nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) pollution by limiting N emissions to soil, water and air and P emissions to water resources which can harm the environment when they leach into the soil and water or evaporate into the air.

ECONUTRI aims to use nature-based solutions to reduce pollution of water, soil and air by nutrient emissions originating from agriculture, including greenhouse gas emissions. Furthermore, the project will train farmers and scientists on the innovative technologies validated and demonstrated by the consortium so they can be used to improve soil, water, and air quality in Europe and China, and contribute in mitigation of global climate change.

This deliverable D1.2, an updated version of D1.1 continues to be a critical component of ECONUTRI's overall goal, as it aims to raise awareness of the project, to share, promote and utilize project results by relevant stakeholders and ultimately, maximize the impact of the project outcomes in EU, associated countries and China. Additionally, it aims to present all actions implemented during the first project period (M1-M18).

The main aims of the updated PDEC D1.2 remain the same as portrayed in D1.1:

1. Widely disseminate the project results to audiences that are expected to use the results in their own work
2. Plan how the partners will exploit / use the project results and manage intellectual property rights (IPR)
3. Communicate the project and its results to multiple audiences beyond the project's own community.

2 OBJECTIVES OF DELIVERABLE D1.2

D1.1 is an intermediate release of the ECONUTRI plan for Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation (PDEC). The main objective of the DEC activities is to promote the project's innovative aspects and maximize its impact by widely sharing outcomes with stakeholders and the public.

The 1st PDEC, developed by CETRI with the active involvement of all partners, was released by month 6 of the project. It served as a valuable resource for partners to use it as guidance for their various DEC activities. In the current (2nd) release of the PDEC, developed with full partner engagement by CETRI, the effectiveness of the DEC strategy will be evaluated by analysing the communication tools used, and adjustments will be implemented if required. Furthermore, being a dynamic document, this plan will be used as the primary input for drafting release 3 of the PDEC at month 42, as outlined in the DoA.

Continuous support from the project community will aid dissemination efforts, fostering the exploitation of all outcomes. Maintaining high project visibility and ongoing stakeholder engagement are crucial for building project awareness, maximizing potential for exploitation, and ensuring accountability that justifies the use of public funds to support this Innovation Action project.

3 DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

Dissemination and communication activities will be complementary and synergistic, targeting a wide range of stakeholders. Partners will **disseminate the project results** to audiences that are expected to use the results in their own work, including scientific community in nutrient management, farmers, companies in the agro-food sector, policymakers, authorities. They will also **communicate the project and its results** to multiple audiences beyond the project's own community including investors, media and the public.

Collectively, the approach will inform and reach out to society, highlighting the importance of applying advanced nutrient management strategies in agriculture. All dissemination and communication activities will be precisely targeted and tailored to each group of intended project stakeholders and will continue after the project's end. This will be achieved by scaling up the application of the 24 innovative technologies deployed by ECONUTRI, based on the exploitation plans of the respective partners which are still in progress and will be decided as results become available.

4 TARGET AUDIENCE AND KEY MESSAGES

The importance of identifying the target audience for dissemination and communication activities highlighting the need for tailored messages aligned with project objectives was elaborated in the 1st release of the PDEC. No changes are necessary for the 2nd release as the strategy remains consistent. Any adjustments to message wording and tone deemed necessary as the project progresses will be incorporated in the final release of the PDEC.

Table 1 - Target Groups

Targeted groups in EU & China	How to reach them	Key message
Farming Industry (FI): Farmers, farming associations, cooperatives, Chambers of Agriculture, agribusiness professionals, advisors.	Exhibitions, fairs, workshops, media.	Reduce fertilizers cost, grow healthier products, contribute to pollution reduction, protect your own health.
Agro-food Companies (AC): ICT/nutrient management / precision agriculture / IOT / smart farming companies, traders, technology providers.	B2B meetings, invitation at project events and workshops, online and face to face meetings, social media.	Substantial profits for investing in a new generation of agricultural innovations. Access a new network of farming stakeholders in EU and China,
Authorities (A): local, regional, Ministries (agriculture, economy, environment), standardization and certification bodies, statistical offices.	F2F meetings, invitation to project events / workshops.	Creation of opportunities for growth, environment protection, new jobs, citizen-centered products.
Policy Makers (PM): experts on regulatory/policy issues related to Nutrients management, environmental organisations, NGOs.	Online and face to face meetings, invitation to project events & workshops.	ECONUTRI will incorporate innovations in nutrient management implementing relevant directives.
Scientific Community (SC): Leading researchers in the key areas of nutrients management, smart farming, IoT. Research Centers and Universities.	Publications, articles, conferences, workshops, research networks, clustering	All data created /collected during the project, not bound to IPR constraints, will be available on open royalty-free basis

Research Projects (RP): Horizon Europe, Horizon 2020, PRIMA, LIFE+, other EU or Chinese funding streams on addressing agricultural pollution issues.	Clustering activities, common workshops.	Let's partner up to maximize our combined impact on clean environment and reach as many stakeholders as possible.
Investors (I): Funding bodies, private equity firms, venture capital investors, innovation brokers	B2B meetings, invitation to project events & workshops.	High ROI by investing in the ECONUTRI technologies and innovations
Media (M): Websites, portals, popular You Tubers, journalists, internet, social media influencers, local TV stations	Targeted articles, videos, infographics, advertisements.	Learn about our EU funded project promoting reduction of pollution from agriculture.
General public(GP): citizens, individuals interested in climate change and environmental issues.	Social media, public events, publications videos, website.	Learn about the European-Chinese effort to reduce pollution from intensive agriculture.

5 DISSEMINATION PLAN

In D1.1, various significant dissemination channels were outlined based on the GA. These are summarized below in Table 2, along with the achievements attained thus far. However, additional dissemination channels have been used over the 18-month project duration, also listed below in Table 2. A notable update for implementing dissemination and open science practices is the creation of the Zenodo community of Econutri <https://zenodo.org/communities/econutri>, where the two publications acknowledging Econutri as well as the deliverables submitted thus far, have been uploaded.

Table 2- Dissemination Tools

Dissemination tool	Performance Indicators in P1	Performance Indicators in P2	Achievements April 2024
Publications	20 peer-reviewed journals	20 peer-reviewed journals	2
Official EU Key Tools Horizon Results Platform, Horizon Dashboard, CORDIS, Innovation Radar (IR), EU magazines as Euronews, Horizon Magazine, Project Stories, research*euresearch magazine.	Use of all Key Tools. 5 articles published at EU magazines	6 popular articles published at EU magazines	none
Articles published in smart farming and environmental magazines.	at least 5 articles	at least 5 articles	none
ECONUTRI Innovation handbook (publicly available and free to download)	>1000 views /downloads	3500 new downloads	Due date month 40
Presentations in Conferences	No specific KPI	-	25
Press releases	No specific KPI	-	5
Organization of Events	At least 2 Stakeholder Conferences	-	5 General Conferences
Networking with other projects Under HORIZON-CL6-2022-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-03, other H2020 / HEU projects	No specific KPI	-	Networking with Trans4num and Pestnu
Patents	No specific KPI	-	none

The forthcoming section will provide a detailed overview of all the dissemination activities carried out by the partners until month 18.

5.1 Dissemination Actions covering the period from November 2022 to April 2024

Since the start of ECONUTRI the following partners undertook various dissemination activities addressing the Farming Industry, Agrofood companies, Scientific community, local and regional authorities and the general public at fairs and exhibitions. The details of the activities are presented below:

- **AUA (P1)** organized /took part in the following activities:
 - Submitted a press release in a Greek radio station in Ierapetra, Crete on 7 Dec. 2023 spreading the ECONUTRI voice in Crete, a high stakeholder regional area full of greenhouses.
 - Organized three conferences,
 1. "New technologies aiming to reduce water and nutrient requirements in greenhouse crops" in Preveza, Greece on 16 Jan. 2023,
 2. "New Technologies to reduce consumption of water and fertilizers in greenhouse crops" in Crete, Greece on 17 March 2023.
 3. "Sustainable fertilisation of Greenhouse vegetables" in Marathon, Attica on 12 Feb. 2023
 - Attended the kick-off meeting of the sister project "Trans4num" at the University of Hohenheim in Stuttgart on 22 Feb. 2023. In this meeting the Coordinators of ECONUTRI and Trans4num discussed opportunities for **networking** and **clustering** events as key strategies for enhancing collaboration and knowledge-sharing among similar projects.
 - Participated in many conferences:
 - In Crete on 8 April 2023 in Ierapetra and on 9 April 2023 in Heraklion, which were organised by local agricultural organisations, about the EU's new common agricultural policy and current innovation programs funded by the EU. The AUA presentations were aimed at promoting the objectives of ECONUTRI, disseminating the use of the DSS NUTRISense by local greenhouse growers and registering local organisations and actors in the stakeholder group of the project.
 - In Bucharest, in the [9th South-Eastern Europe Symposium on Vegetables and Potatoes](#)", on 5-9 September, 2023, with a presentation titled "Precise Fertilization in Greenhouse Crops Using Modern Decision Support Systems to Conserve Fertilizers and Reduce Water Resource Pollution".
 - In Crete on the 21st of Sept. 2023 in Tympaki and on the 22nd of Sept. 2023 in Ierapetra, about sustainable fertigation and use of biostimulants in greenhouse crops, where the ECONUTRI project was presented to many stakeholders. The coordinator also visited the Growers Cooperative Psaris in Southern-East Crete.
 - In Crete on 29 October - 2 November 2023 in Heraklio, at the 31st Conference of the Greek Society for Horticultural Science ([EEEE](#)).
 - In Bologna, Italy on Jan. 18 2024, at 3rd International Workshop on Vertical Farming ([VertiFarm2024](#)) with a presentation titled: "Optimization of nutrient supply in leafy vegetables grown in vertical farming using the Decision Support System NUTRISense".
 - Training seminar for growers and agronomists on "Recent Trends in sustainable fertilisation of vegetable crops" as an EU Green Week Partner Event in Cyprus on 6-7 June 2023.

- Presented the Econutri-Project during a summer school of the Erasmus+ project “Best Microgardens” in Bologna, on June 7, 2023.
- Participated as an exhibitor from 21 to 23 Sept. 2023 to the 2nd Agri-Innovation Expo 2023, an exhibition for presenting innovative research ideas to the public. Econutri was showcased during this event.
- Joined a press conference on 2 Oct. 2023 at the state-of-the-art hydroponic greenhouse, Intelligent Green Crops (IGC), located at Kastro Viotias, Greece. IGC is a stakeholder of Econutri, which produces high-quality lettuce in a moving gutter system with recirculating nutrient solution.
- Participated In Thessaloniki, Greece on 1-4 February 2024 at AGROTICA2024, where the spinoff company NUTRISENSE PC, established by AUA, was an exhibitor with its own stand, disseminating the innovations elaborated in ECONUTRI project.
- Organised an open day on 21 March, 2024 at AUA, with the aim of disseminating the technologies it develops within the framework of national and European research programs.
- **UAL (P2) and COEXPHAL (12)** coorganized and submitted:
 - Four different press releases in 4 different Spanish online newspapers.
 - 18 July 2023, a course for farmers, "Technological innovation in greenhouses: the future of production" and presented Econutri.
- **UAL** participated in the conferences:
 - in Almeria Spain, on 26-28 June 2023 at the HORCHIMODEL 2023
<http://www2.ual.es/horchimodel2021>
 - in Cancun, Mexico, on 22 October 2023 at the IVth International Symposium on New Technologies for Sustainable Greenhouse Systems -presentation on the use of the VegSyst-DSS
<http://www.greensys2023.org/>
- **UTH (P3)** organized the following activities:
 - Presentation of ECONUTRI UTH activities in more than 150 students (primary, secondary, high school and university students) that visited the Pilot Greenhouse Park of the University of Thessaly.
 - 4-5 October 2023 in Volos, Greece, Joint event with PestNu Green-Deal project at UTH facilities
 - 19-20 October 2023, in Athens Greece participated in the 13th Panhellenic Conference of the Society of Agricultural Engineers of Greece (EGME),. Title of the paper: “COMBINATION OF CUCUMBER AND MELON CROPS IN A CASCADE HYDROPONIC SYSTEM”
 - 22 October 2023 in Cancun, Mexico at GreenSys2023: International Symposium on New Technologies for Sustainable Greenhouse Systems, <https://www.greensys2023.org>
<https://www.actahort.org/members/symposiaa?action=abstractforcoauthor&abstractforcoauthorlink=zKXtwXmtwXm-1968085-twXmKoXMBzKX/>
- **IGZ (P4)** organized the following events:
 - 19-29 Jan. 2023, in Berlin Germany, an exhibition “Internationale Grüne Woche Berlin”
 - 24-27 Jan. 2023, in Essen Germany, an exhibition “International Plant Messe” (IPM)
 - 17-26 Jan. 2023 participated in the commercial fair Berlin Green
<https://www.gruenewoche.de/>

- 23-26 Jan. 2023 participated in the commercial fair IPM-Essen, <https://www.ipmessen.de/world-trade-fair/>
 - 26 June 2023 in Almeria, Spain at ISHS HORCHIMODEL 2023 <http://www2.ual.es/horchimodel2021>
 - 22 October 2023 in Cancun, Mexico at GreenSys2023: International Symposium on New Technologies for Sustainable Greenhouse Systems, <https://www.greensys2023.org/>
- **WUR (P6)** attended the following events:
- 29 Jan. - 2 Feb. 2023 Xth International Symposium on Irrigation in Horticultural Crops, <https://www.ishs.org/symposium/738>
 - 22 October 2023 IVth International Symposium on New Technologies for Sustainable Greenhouse Systems, Cancún, México, presentation/poster on the topic of DSS for irrigation in greenhouse crops <http://www.greensys2023.org/>
 - 12-16 Nov 2023 First visit to China for Chinese KOM with **UAL**
 - 6 April 2024 in Nieuwe Wetering, Kom in De Kas Exhibition “Promotion and explanation of the Virtual Lysimeter” and ECONUTRI at the yearly event for general public.
 - 5-19 April 2024 - Second visit of **UAL** and **WUR** to Chinese ECONUTRI partners and Stakeholders
 - Together with **LGNL(P11)**:
 - 22 June 2023 in Naaldwijk, NL organised a "Water Day" workshop aimed to inform Dutch growers with essential knowledge and skills resulting from Econutri research to elevate agricultural practices and increase productivity.
 - 21 Sept. 2023 in Naaldwijk, NL organized a pitch event to inform growers about the DSS virtual lysimeter, WP3.3
 - 12 October 2023 in Bleiswijk, NL participated in a workshop to inform growers on optimizing irrigation by means of the virtual lysimeter
 - 5 Dec. 2023 in Honselersdijk NL participated in the “Organic growers years meeting” informing growers about Econutri results.
 - 12 Dec. 2023 Honselersdijk NL , organized a workshop for cucumber growers.
 - 3 March 2024 in Bleiswijk, NL, organized a workshop to present progress report of the DSS virtual Lysimeter
- **NIBIO (P7)** took part in the following activities:
- 22 Nov 2022 showcased ECONUTRI at the NIBIO conference in the context of EU-China research collaborations.
 - 5 Dec 2023 online workshop on World Soil Day – (non-scientific publication)
- **ARI (8)**
- 6 July 2023 in Cyprus, at a pitch event: CLUSTER advanCing youth and women social InClUSion in The MEditerRanean
 - 3 April 2024 in Tochni, Larnaca (Cyprus) at a conference Climate change and adaptability, with the aim of sustainable water management
- **UNITO(P10)**
- 7-10 Nov 2023 in Rimini, Italy participation in conference Ecomondo – The green technology expo

- 22-24 Nov. 2023 organised the 2nd General Assembly of Econutri in Turin
- **UTAD (P11)** attended the 5th Iberian Meeting on Pastures and Forages, 17-20 April 2023. <https://www.pastos2023.com/inscripciones-reunion-iberica-pastos-forrajes/>
 - Published a paper: Martins, J. A., Marta-Costa, A., Lucas, M. R., & Santos, M. (2024). Sustainability in Mountain Viticulture: Insights from a Case Study in the Portuguese Douro Region. *Sustainability*, 16(5), 2050.
- **COEXPHAL (12)** organized a workshop on 1 Dec. 2023, on digital technology for agroecological systems. This workshop was directed to field technicians and growers.
- **ATB (16)**
 - 23 May 2023 in Dessau, Germany participation in an “annual meeting of the Task Force on Reactive Nitrogen (TFRN)” where, Econutri was introduced.
 - 12 Sept. 2023 in Cambridge, UK participation in RAMIRAN Conference “ Managing organic resources in a changing environment” where Econutri was displayed.
 - 10-11 Oct. 2023 in Darmstadt, Germany, participation in a conference “Emission from Livestock Farming-2023: Collect, assess, mitigate”
 - Jointly with **EV ILVO (21)** on 12-13 Oct 2023 organised a workshop on emission measurement and standardization in ATB project sites, exploring the technicalities of Econutri work and OTICE sensor calibration.
 - 15-17 Nov.2023 in Arhus Denmark, 1st meeting to work on the revision of the UNECE GD on ammonia abatement.
- **INHORT (18)**
 - 6 Dec 2023 in Skierniewice, Poland organized a training on Fertilizer microbiological products effective in improving the quality of crops and soil fertility.
 - 17-18 Jan 2024 in Kielce, Poland at a workshop/fair 14th edition of the TSW Fruit and Vegetable Growing Fair
 - 13-16 Feb 2024 in Nuremberg, Germany at trade fair Biofach - World’s Leading Trade Fair for Organic Food
 - 26 Feb. 2024 in Bratuszyn, Poland at a conference Healthy Earth Circle Academy
 -
- **LGNL (P20)** organized the following activities:
 - An online meeting on grower’s soil bound crops on 19 Jan. 2023
 - An online meeting with organic growers on 8 Feb. 2023.
 - A workshop “Future proof cultivation for soil crop” in De Kwakel, NL on 23 Nov. 2022
 - Published an article on the Implementation of ECONUTRI, on 9 Feb. 2023 on their website, to make the growers aware of the beginning of the project in The Netherlands.
- **EV ILVO (P21)** organized the following events:
 - 12 Jan. 2023 in Ghent, Belgium participated in a fair “Agri Flanders”
 - 19 Jan. 2023 in Melle, Belgium organized a training seminar about “Ammonia-reducing measures: What's in the pipeline? Is there any news from the scientific research?”
 - 24 March 2023 in Melle, Belgium, a conference, Vemis seminar, about emissions <https://ilvo.vlaanderen.be/nl/agenda/vemis-studiedag-vlaams-emissieonderzoek-in-de-kijker>
 - 3 March 2023, a Communication campaign in EV ILVO newsletter <https://email.ilvo.vlaanderen.be/t/t-e-fdihkkgk-whyurkkhd-yu/>

- 6 June 2023 in ILVO Merelbeke (Belgium) a training seminar, informing growers about Econutri.
- 8 June 2023 in Brussels, Belgium participated in the conference “Nature Network Annual Event”
- **HAAS-P23**
 - June 5-7 2023 Organization of Workshop NIBIO-HAAS Conference 2023 Harbin, China
- **NAU/CAU/HAAS P26/P27/P23**
 - May 2023 Organization of Workshop Discussion on the progress of subtasks regarding biofertilisers development, in Nanjing, China
- **SVG/CAU P25/P27**
 - November 2023 Organization of Conference in Shouguang, Shandong, China
 - “China National Vegetable Quality Standards Summit Forum”
 - Exhibition “China Shouguang International Vegetable Seed Industry Expo”
- **JHI (P30)** highlighted its experimental platform, and intercropping work
 - At the PLEN (Plant and Environment) PhD Student Annual Conference on ‘Science & Industry’, held at The Royal Danish Academy of Sciences and Letters, Copenhagen University, 3 Nov. 2022.
 - At the "Next Generation Dairying Workshop" of the Hannah Dairy Research Foundation, held at the Moredun Research Institute, Edinburgh, 21-22 Nov. 2022.
<https://www.journalofdairyresearch.org/next-generation-dairying-2022.html>
 - June 6 2023 in Scotston Farm, by Dundee participated in a workshop organised by Scottish Organic Producers Association (SOPA) to discuss RUE on organic farms.
 - 12 June 2023, podcast in which discussed about legume inclusion to meet environmental, human, and animal health i.e., One Health objectives
 - Published a paper by Pietro Iannetta. Can find it here
<https://zenodo.org/records/10894071>
 - Participation in several conferences
 - 26 Sept. 2023 in Oxford Uni., UK at “Beans as a Vehicle for Transforming Food System Outcomes”
 - 20 Nov 2023 in Moredun Inst. Edinburgh, Scotland UK, at “HDRF Next Generation Dairying Conference”
 - 29 Nov 2023 Dundee, Scotland UK at “Leg Up 4 Legumes”

5.2 Dissemination Actions in the future

To promote project participation through ECONUTRI communication channels, CETRI has asked partners to inform both AUA and itself about any new events they will be participating in at least one week before the event. Following the event, partners are asked to utilize the 'ECONUTRI D&C reporting template' (See Annex 2) to monitor progress. The participating partner fills out the document and sends it back to both AUA and CETRI. For saving time in the gathering process, it is also available in the ECONUTRI repository, the One drive, accessible to all European countries but not to the Chinese partners.

As the project progresses, partners will plan and schedule activities/events in which they intend to participate and disseminate the project results. All partners are asked to fill out the 'ECONUTRI D&C reporting for future activities template' in order to have a more efficient dissemination plan. A preliminary list of planned events is outlined in section 5.2.1 in Table 3.

5.2.1 Events planned for the years 2024/2025 (after M18)

Table 3 - Events Planned after M18

Partner	Date	Name of Event and link
AUA – P1	23-26 September 2024	ISHS - I International Symposium on Protected Cultivation, Nettings and Screens for Mild Climates) - Organised by the coordinator of ECONUTRI (AUA) https://promicli.athens2024.org/
	27 September 2024	<u>Stakeholder Conference</u> co-organised by ECONUTRI, TRANS4NUM and PESTNU. In Athens, Greece at the AUA campus.
NIBIO UTAD UNITO	7 May 2024	https://nibio.pameldingssystem.no/sluttseminar-for-mafigold-og-presentasjon-av-econutri-7-mai-2024 in Stavanger, Norway
NIBIO CAU	18-19 June 2024	20-year anniversary workshop for NIBIO-China collaborations, in Moss, Norway
ILVO	24-26 Sept. 2024	EmiLi 2024 conference in Valencia, Spain
ATB	17 June 2024	Workshop: Resolving the Global Nitrogen Dilemma-Opportunities and Challenges in Arhus, Denmark
INHORT	10 May 2024	Microbiological preparations in agriculture and environmental protection (in Polish) https://www.iung.pl/2024/02/01/preparaty-mikrobiologiczne-w-rolnictwie/
INHORT	17-18 June 2024	8TH National Microbiological Symposium "Metagenomes of Different Environments" https://www.kul.pl/viii-ogolnopolskie-symposium-mikrobiologiczne,art_105326.html
INHORT	17-20 Sept 2024	IV International Organic Fruit Symposium and II Organic Vegetable Symposium (OrgHort 2024) in Warszawa, Poland https://orghort2024.pl/

Below are some of the activities planned to be implemented by ECONUTRI partners during the project life (See also Table 3)

By AUA-Coordinator- Laboratory of Vegetable Crops

- Six in-situ training activities for growers and agronomists on sustainable nutrient management in agriculture and the use of the DSS NUTRISENSE developed by AUA to support sustainable fertilization practices
- One summer school in the Summer of 2025
- Two stakeholder conferences, one in September 2024 and one in 2025
- One hackathon in 2025 to fine-tune nutrient management plans and promote the application of DSS by growers and advisors
- Visits to farmers for in-situ training on the use of the DSS developed by the AUA team of ECONUTRI

- Creation of demonstration videos
- Electronic and printed leaflets about the DSS and technologies developed by AUA to support smart nutrient management plans and optimize recycling of the fertigation effluents.
- Radio interviews in local radio stations in regions with extensive vegetable production
- At least three scientific papers in peer-reviewed international scientific journals

By AUA- Laboratory of Viticulture

- Organize a dissemination event (conference or workshop) and planning to publish an article

By AUA- Smart Farming Technology Group

- Field demonstrations measuring Vegetation Indexes (VIs) with AUA's Drones & Augmenta's Smart Tractor-Mounted Camera.
- Field Demonstrations of precision slurry application with the control system that will be developed by AUA.
- Present the results from the experimental fields to related and linked to ECONUTRI projects such as ICAERUS & SmartBiC.
- Social Media promotion through the pages of SFTG.
- Regular dissemination efforts such as presentations in potential conferences, fairs and project meetings.

By UTH (P3)

- Radio interviews in local radio stations in regions with extensive vegetable production.
- At least one article publication to local agricultural magazines.
- At least one scientific paper in peer-reviewed international scientific journals.
- High school students, BSc, and MSc student visits as part of a training activity session to get familiar with all technologies used under the frame of the project.

By IGZ (P4)

- Planning to submit a minimum of four scientific peer-reviewed articles within the time frame of the project.
- Annual participation on international commercial fairs in Germany IPM and Green Week as exhibitor.
- Press-release in Germany.

By WUR (P6)

- Articles:
 - 1) In the magazine (Dutch) 'Onder glas' (Horticulture) about improved irrigation to achieve the zero liquid discharge goals.
 - 2) In the magazine: (Dutch) Groenten+Fruit (vegetables and fruits): about maximum recycling by using increased Na and Cl levels in drainage water.

By NIBIO (P7)

- Field days for farmers and horticulture, where the project and its results are presented
- Online presentation: A public project webpage for ECONUTRI presented on NIBIO's website
- Articles in two magazines for Norwegian farmers: "Bondevennen" and "Norsk landbruk":
 - 1) On recycling of nutrients in animal manure (methodologies) and
 - 2) On planning of fertilizing with new organic fertilizers based on waste components

By UTAD (P11)

- Organization of two seminars with growers and advisers to present and demonstrate the results:

- 1) *Maize intercropping with legumes for forage quality improvement (September 2024 or 2025, with an open day at a demonstration field)*
 - 2) Slurry liquid fraction treatment technologies for ammonia and GHG emission reduction and better crop nutrient recovery (2024)
- Testing new composting solutions at commercial level - Transfer of knowledge on composting technologies to the stakeholder SIRO (commercial composting and plant substrates company, <https://portal.siro.pt/us/programs/cindex.aspx>).
 - Field activity: From monoculture to consociations/intercropping: the added value for biodiversity: with this field activity, we aim showing the importance of intercropping as an added-value to halt biodiversity lost in European agriculture. Ecological indicators will be used to tackle this issue. Proposed date Spring 2025.

By COEXPHAL(P12)

As an association of grower organizations, COEXPHAL will mostly take care of spreading the knowledge among the end-users of the ECONUTRI technology developed, namely field advisors and growers in Almería. The University of Almeria (UAL) (P2) and COEXPHAL will closely collaborate in scientific dissemination. COEXPHAL will also organize:

- **Articles.** Publish in printed monthly magazine ('AenVerde'), that directly reaches 2,500 growers in Almería and is freely available in all cooperatives. A first article will be written when the work in the greenhouses starts, explaining the objectives and expected results. A minimum of 3 articles will be published.
- **Field demonstrations.** Once the first results have been reached, i.e., after the first crop cycle in which the proposed methods have been tested and evaluated, we will organise demonstrations in the greenhouses for growers and field technicians of the cooperatives where the practical work takes place. We expect to do this in at least 4 occasions.
- **Study days.** COEXPHAL will organize a large number of study days and seminars every year, directed to either the general public or to the growers and field advisors of one of the associated companies. The findings of ECONUTRI will be presented in at least three of these events.
- **Social media.** COEXPHAL has a wide network of followers in the social media (facebook, twitter), as well as a continuous presence through the on-line version of 'AenVerde'. This allows the spread of short videos, such as recorded experiences of growers and investigators or technical instructions.

By LGNL (P20)

In cooperation with partner **WUR (P6)** a number of dissemination & communication activities are lined up.

- A page/dashboard on the website www.glastuinbouwwaterproof.nl (the greenhouse horticulture waterproof website)
- Videos/articles with growers (who work with the virtual lysimeter)
- Online presentation/video with explanation (how the virtual lysimeter works)
- A demo model (so one can try it out and see how it could benefit their company)
- Organization of events and smaller meetings with growers and advisers to present and demonstrate the results

By EV ILVO (P21)

- Planning dissemination events on Agriculture Day 17 Sept. 2024

5.2.2 Stakeholder engagement events

- Two stakeholder conferences are planned during the lifetime of the project. The first stakeholder conference will take place in Athens, in 27 September 2024 as a satellite event in the I International

Symposium of the ISHS on Protected Cultivation, Nettings and Screens for Mild Climates (organised by AUA with D. Savvas and Th. Bartzanas as conveners).

It is already displayed on the Econutri website: <https://econutri-project.eu/events/satelite-event-of-the-i-international-symposium-on-protected-cultivation-nettings-and-screens-for-mild-climates/>

Stakeholder engagement: ECONUTRI will engage with a wide range of stakeholders throughout the project, including industry representatives, policy makers, and NGOs, to ensure that its research is relevant and useful to those who will be affected by its outcomes. ECONUTRI has organised centrally a registration platform for the core stakeholders in its webpage, where they can register upon our suggestion (invitation) and fill in a Letter of Intent. This platform is planned to act as a stakeholder forum to exchange information and transfer knowledge and experience. Knowledge and experience transfer can be bilateral i.e., from partners to stakeholders (mainly knowledge) and from stakeholders to partners (mainly practical experiences). The stakeholders that have signed the letter of Intent until now are the following:

- | | |
|---|---|
| Confirmation Letters | Cyprus - Georgios Vassiliades - Agrowise Ltd |
| Lol-Translations | Cyprus - Loizos Tofas - Planty |
| Presentations of Italian Stakeholders in GA Torino | Greece - Antonios Gkasdrogkas - KILELER PLANTS |
| 01Copy of Stakeholders - Emails (003) | Greece - Archontisa Dermitzaki - Farmwoman in Ierapetra Crete |
| Belgium - Jean Reusens - Energia | Greece - Costas Philippacopoulos-Intelligent Green Crops |
| Belgium - Katrien Boussey - Vlaams Departement Landbouw en Visserij | Greece - Dimitrios Kouvas - SCIENTACT AE |
| Belgium - Lisa Dejonghe - Inagro | Greece - Dimitris Antoniadis - Municipality of Volos |
| Belgium - Mark Willems - Vlaamse Landmaatschappij | Greece - Georgios Polioudakis - Polioudakis-Anthokomikh |
| China - 564176907@qq.com - Wslesso | Greece - Ioannis Kalliantzis - Agroktima Kalliantzi |
| China - 5226283089@163.com - WANHUIBIOTECH | Greece - Iordanis Samanidis -THESgi |
| China - Chunbin Geng (944149293@qq.com) -Baoding Ruiwosi Environmental Technology Co., Ltd. | Greece - Konstantinos Nikoloudis - Agrobusiness (Greenhouse cropping) |
| China - Doudou Guo - Beijing Jingwa Agricultural Science and Technology | Greece - Nick Moutevelis - ALAGRO |
| China - Haijun Zhao (Yms087)-Harvest | Greece - Nikoletos Theofanis - Farmer - Greenhouse cropping |
| China - Hongbin Ni (603395649@qq.com) - Shandong Borunde Agricultural Technology | Greece - Nikos Epitropakis - Producer in Crete |
| China - Jun Ren - Bei Cai Yuan agricultural technology development | Greece - Theodoros Amanatidis - Drama Greenhouses |
| China - Junjian chen - Zhongye Modern Agric. Technology | Greece - Vaios Argyrakis - B-D Argyrakis Agricultural Lab Ltd. |
| China - Junjie Liu -Northeast Institute of Geography and Agroecology, Chinese Academy of Sciences China | Greece - Vangelis Vassiliadis - AGROSTIS |
| China - Lianying Jia-Yipu Run (Hainan) Agricultural Technology | Italy - Andrea Repossini - Coldiretti Torino |
| China - Ling Guan - Shenyang Qiushi agricultural science and Technology development Co Ltd. | Italy - Daniel EL CHAMI-TIMAC AGRO Italia S.P.A. |
| China - Qixuan Wang-Zhonde Fertilizer (Yanta) | Italy - Luigi Andreis - CIA Agricoltori Italiani |
| China - sllhjt@139.com - TAI HE WU ZE.. | Italy - Mayr Josef Biogas Wipptal |
| China - Tianwen Liang -GuangdongKaimirui Fertilizer Technology | Italy - Paolo Gariglio - Agricoltore |
| China - wangkang@hongfujituan.com - HOF0 Agriculture | Italy - Roberto Abellocio - Confagricoltura Cuneo |
| China - Wenxiang He - Jingmen Famax Agricultural Technology | Netherlands - Anne-Marie van Bussel - DE HUEVE -INNOVATIE |
| China - Xiangmin Yu - Beijing Kalyin organic Fertilizer production (123940570@qq.com) | Netherlands - Pieter Gillesen-Gillesen |
| China - Xiangming Yu - Beijing Kailyin organic Fertilizer production | Netherlands - Pieter Vlaar-Vertify |
| China - Xinxu Li - Beijing Cuihu Agricultural Technology Co. Ltd. | Portugal - Diogo Pinhol-Monte Silveira Bio farm |
| China - Yan Li-Beijing Aike Saier Certification Center | Portugal - Hartmut Nestler-SIRO |
| China - Yan Shi - Shared Harvest (Beijing) Agriculture Development Co Ltd. | Spain - Emilio Perez Lopez - COPROHNIJAR |
| China - Yangjingxiu-Humic Growth | Spain - Joaquin Soriano Fernandez - IKOSTECH |
| China - Yunhe Zhao - Protio (Beijing) Biotechnology Co. Ltd. | Spain - Juan Antonio Gonzalez Real - APROA |
| China - Yuyuan Liu - Zhongnongfutong | Spain - Juan Tomas Cano - Hortiespana |
| China - Zhuo Han (33942544@qq.com) -V Land | Spain - Maria Isabel Rubio Fernandez - Murgiverde |
| China- Baogang Xu -Weifang Huijinhai IOT Technology | United Arab Emirates -Thanos Papanikolaou - Heaven Farms |

Figure 1 - Econutri Stakeholders

5.2.3 Clustering activities & EU-China Cooperation <https://china.enrichcentres.eu/>

The clustering activities and the EU-China Cooperation will be coordinated by SPI, leader of Task 1.4 in WP1. ECONUTRI will **cluster** with other funded projects under HORIZON-CL6-2022-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-03, and other relevant H2020 / Horizon Europe projects. This will create a community for knowledge and dealing with practices towards a global transition to sustainable farming systems. Engaged actors will learn more about each other, will find common issues, will share good practices and digital innovations, and will explore possibilities for future collaboration and knowledge exchange. This networking will also contribute to formulating specific policy recommendations in nutrient management technologies.

The dissemination and exploitation plans will be reinforced through clustering activities. ECONUTRI aims to focus on identifying more clusters and projects (in addition to “Trans4num” and PestNu”) that undertake similar activities with ECONUTRI and to establish common pathways for dissemination and exploitation.

A collaboration with the “**ENRICH in China**” initiative will be established, with the aim of organising one joint webinar with Chinese agricultural companies from the “ENRICH in China” network, together with the European Partners and share knowledge on best practices in nutrients management. Additionally, the news and outcomes of the project will be promoted by the channels of “ENRICH in China” (its own network, webpage, and social media – WeChat, LinkedIn and Twitter).

- ECONUTRI will organize complementary activities between EU and Chinese actors to strengthen their scientific and commercial ties;
- Disseminate the project results to targeted stakeholders in EU and China to create a knowledge ecosystem. Involved actors will exchange experiences, best practices, plus identify and co-develop innovative nutrient management approaches;
- “ENRICH in China” series webinars as a training session or clustering activities to share knowledge and increase visibility of ECONUTRI.

6 COMMUNICATION PLAN

The objectives of the communication plan align with those presented in the first PDEC D1.1: to engage in activities and utilize tools aimed at enhancing awareness of the project, its main goals and objectives across multiple audiences beyond the project's own community. These efforts seek to inform and reach out to society, emphasizing the importance of innovative nutrient management technologies in reducing environmental footprints. In the initial six-month period, in D1.1 the communication plan included the visual identity of the project, the website, the leaflet, the roll up banner and the social media profiles which are also included in this updated version for consistency. Further communication actions have been implemented and are displayed below with details.

6.1 Visual Identity

The communication tools are the project’s visual identity. They have been developed in the first four months of the project and will be used for the ECONUTRI project and furthermore for the network that will be established during the project’s lifetime and beyond. All the tools have been designed by WP1 leader CETRI. The ECONUTRI visual identity consists of:

- ECONUTRI Logo and colour guide
- ECONUTRI Deliverable template
- ECONUTRI Presentation template
- ECONUTRI Agenda template
- ECONUTRI Minutes template

6.1.1 ECONUTRI Logo

After the kick-off meeting, CETRI distributed the logo to the whole consortium and various file formats for different uses (website, leaflet, social channels), were uploaded in the One drive repository folder. This unique logo is the primary representation of the project and expresses its distinct visual character. (Figure 1)

Figure 2 - ECONUTRI logo

Furthermore, for Horizon Europe projects, all communication forms shall have the EU logo and the funding statement (Figure 2).

Figure 3 - EU logo

6.1.2 ECONUTRI colours

The ECONUTRI colour schemes shown in Figure 3 are the two colours used in the logo and can be utilized throughout the project materials to organize and emphasize various sections of content. These colours will also influence the colour scheme of all other communication materials (templates, leaflets, rollup banner, social media platforms, articles)

CMYK & WEB COLOURS

Figure 4- ECONUTRI logo colours

6.1.3 ECONUTRI Templates

CETRI, AUA and METEC have created a number of ECONUTRI templates in order to maintain consistency in the layout and appearance of all project uses. All the templates feature the project logo, the EU logo, and the ECONUTRI colours. In order to utilize the templates as effective communication tools, all partners have been instructed to use the correct templates for their intended purposes. The templates that have been developed so far are:

- **ECONUTRI Deliverable template**
- **ECONUTRI Presentation template**
- **ECONUTRI Agenda template**
- **ECONUTRI Minutes template**

6.2 Website

In today’s digital world the website serves as the primary dissemination and communication tool. The ECONUTRI website www.econutri-project.eu/ has been launched since the beginning of the project by CETRI. Over the course of 18 months, the website structure has undergone several modifications to enhance functionality and user experience while providing additional information. Specifically, the "project" page now includes enriched subpages such as consortium overview, work package structure, partner contributions, and portraits of the external advisory board members. The "outputs" page remains unchanged, while the "Communication & Dissemination" page has been replaced by "Resources," featuring subpages like Articles, Publications, Conferences, Videos, Newsletter, and Promotional material. The "Newsletter" page has been replaced by "News," showcasing all consortium activities. Additionally, the "Stakeholder Engagement" page has been replaced by the "Demonstration sites" page, detailing the eight pilot plant areas. Finally, the new "Stakeholders" page includes three subpages emphasizing stakeholder interaction, including "Why become a stakeholder," "Project Description," and "Letter of Intent," which can be downloaded, signed, and uploaded by interested parties. See the updated website structure in Table 4 below. The ECONUTRI webpage is displayed as screenshot in Annex 1.

Table 4 – ECONUTRI Website structure

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Home	Project	Outputs	Resources	News	Demonstration sites	Stakeholders
	Objective	Public Abstracts	Articles		All 8 sites in subpages	Why become a stakeholder
	Consortium Overview	Public Deliverables	Publications			Project description
	Structure		Conferences			Letter of Intent
	Work Package Structure		Videos			
	Partners		Newsletter			
	Partner contribution		Promotional Material			
	External Advisory Board					

The website has been translated into 10 different languages, spoken by the partners, offering valuable resources to the agricultural sector and ensuring accessibility for a diverse range of users. The ‘News’ page is regularly updated while partners become increasingly engaged and proactive as the project advances. The website includes links to social media platforms such as LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. A few months ago, the Chinese WeChat platform was added, and the latest addition is the YouTube channel, launched two weeks ago. Three new features have been incorporated into the "Home" webpage: an additional button for stakeholders to "APPLY", along with sections for "Latest News" and "Upcoming Events" at the bottom of the homepage.

To monitor the website's impact and performance, Google Analytics has been activated and is regularly monitored. The insights from Google Analytic are presented below.

Website analytics from M4-M18 (February 2023 to 30 April 2024)

- Total users: 2,7961
- Page views: 9,919
- Top users by country: China=359, UK=338, Greece=309, NL 187

6.3 Leaflet

CETRI has produced an ECONUTRI leaflet to be distributed at conferences and other relevant events related to nutrient management in agriculture, across EU countries and China. No changes were required until now.

The project leaflet is a key communication component and will accompany project partners at all communication-related activities. It will serve as the first outreach document of the project that provides an insight into the core objectives, the challenges, the concept, partners, and EU funding programme.

The leaflet is distributed in digital format to all partners, who are responsible for printing it at their own cost and utilizing it at appropriate events.

The leaflet is threefold and it includes: 1) project logo, title and website, 2) partners logos, 3) project information, 4) social media platforms, 5) the challenge, 6) the solution and 7) who benefits

Figure 5 - ECONUTRI 3-fold leaflet

6.4 Roll up banner

A rollup banner has been designed by CETRI to be set up in conferences, workshops and various ECONUTRI-related events. The project logo, title, contact details, logos of the consortium and funding sources have been included to ensure a clear understanding of the project within 5 seconds. No changes were required for the banner.

Figure 6 - ECONUTRI rollup banner

6.5 Social media

Social media is a vital tool in the 21st century that amplifies messages, reaching a wider audience, and allows for interaction through informal communication. A social media strategy has been developed in the first PDEC and in this updated version the analytics of each social media platform, being monitored since February 2023, will be presented to identify which aspects of the strategy are effective and reaching out to the audience. If the effectiveness is not satisfactory then different approaches will be considered. It is important to note that all followers have been acquired organically and not through any sponsorship.

All partners are encouraged to follow and share ECONUTRI social media accounts (Table 5) in order to promote the project, broaden the ECONUTRI community and ultimately reach the 1500 followers as promised in the proposal. CETRI is responsible for ensuring the profiles remain up to date and active with news and relevant posts during and after the project lifetime, with the contribution from all partners.

One of the benefits of social media is that it allows people to connect and communicate with others from all over the world, to participate in discussions on a wide range of topics and also learn and grow from the diverse perspectives and viewpoints of each other.

The use of hashtags helps in this sense and several are incorporated into ECONUTRI posts such as #fertilizers, #nutrients, #NH3emissions, #agrofood, #Chinapartners, #plantnutrition, #HorizonEurope.

It is important to note that the use of the '@' symbol will always be included when referring to the ECONUTRI project on all four social media profiles!

ECONUTRI uses five different social media platforms to target different stakeholder groups: LinkedIn Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and YouTube.

6.5.1 LinkedIn Profile

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/87442162/admin/feed/posts/>

The Econutri LinkedIn account has experienced constant growth since its creation. Below are the project's LinkedIn analytics spanning a period of 365 days, providing insights into its performance over the course of a year (maximum period LinkedIn data is provided).

- Number of Followers: 1,087
- Page views: 2,245
- Number of posts: 73

For the rest of the social media accounts the analytics reflect a small but steady growth, demonstrating promising engagement levels, but there is still potential for further improvement.

6.5.2 Twitter profile

<https://twitter.com/Econutri30>

- Number of Followers: 106
- Number of posts: 65

6.5.3 Facebook profile

<https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100088240593124>

- Number of Followers: 111
- Likes: 78

6.5.4 Instagram profile

<https://www.instagram.com/econutri30/>

- Number of Followers: 91
- Number of posts: 48
- 543 engagements (likes)

6.5.5 YouTube profile

https://www.youtube.com/channel/UcklKut5Fn7_GyDxg31QIW7Q

The YouTube channel, an update to the initial PDEC, was created 20 April 2024 to host videos created within the project. Currently, there are five videos with 95 views and 17 subscribers so far:

- Dr. Dimitrios Savvas, Director of the Laboratory of Vegetable Production, Department of Plant Sciences in the Agricultural University of Athens, is the Coordinator of the Horizon Europe Econutri Project and in this video he is providing general information of the innovative project. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Mz3EJn7r3LY&t=4s>
- Dr. Georgia Ntatsi, an Assistant Professor at the Agricultural University of Athens, is part of the Econutri project. In this video, she introduces an innovative hydroponic system for cultivating tomatoes. This system incorporates Ion Selective Electrodes and Soilless Nutrisense technology, with the goal of optimising the supply of nitrogen and phosphorus, thus minimising pollution of water resources due to leaching and runoff. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vGRBDwTfqlc>
- Presenting the University (UNITO) and their contribution to the Econutri project. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XCJ4MwAggFc&t=8s>
- The kick-off meeting for the Chinese part of the EU-China collaboration project Econutri was successfully held on November 17 2023. With the EU part already underway for a year, Econutri is now running at its full capacity. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TjIwYxTmk54>
- EU partners met with China partners within the Econutri project to share knowledge on soil restoration and greenhouse gas emission reduction. They visited the Kaimirui Base of Ruifeng Ecological Group strengthening even more the China-EU cooperation under the Econutri project. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sJgUAg2NQYQ&t=6s>

6.5.6 E-Newsletter

The purpose of the e-newsletter is to provide an update and highlight major achievements of the project. The project partners have contributed with events they have participated. Interested parties subscribe to the newsletter through the Econutri website and so far, there are 24 subscribers.

- The first issue of the e-newsletter is available on the website under Resources [here](#).
- The second issue of the e-newsletter is available on the website under Resources [here](#).

6.5.7 Visits to school

Throughout the duration of the project, each partner is required to visit at least one school with a total of 28 schools. So far the visits are:

- **ARI** (P8) arranged students participating in the Erasmus program from Veria (Greece) to visit Tochni, 3 April 2024 and Xylotymbou 10 April 2024, experimental stations at ARI focusing on the EcoNutri field trials. During their visit, they received training and informative sessions. The purpose of the students' visit was aligned with their participation in the Erasmus program titled: 'Climate Change and Adaptability for Sustainable Water Management' (Program No. 2023-1-EL01-KA121-VET-00014088).
- On Tuesday, April 16th, **ARI** Econutri team conducted a school visit to Latsia located in Nicosia, Cyprus. During the visit, the researchers delivered interactive presentations and distributed leaflets to the teaching staff within the framework of the EcoNutri project. The primary objective was to disseminate knowledge among the teaching staff, with the subsequent intention to extend this awareness to the students.
- On January 18 2024, **AUA** visited the 3rd primary school of Argiroupoli, introducing students to the world of agriculture and the Econutri project. They showcased the need for innovative practices to reduce pollution and protect the planet for future generations.

All communication tools with their respective KPIs and the achievements of the 18-month period are described below in Table 5.

Table 5 – Communication tools

Tools/Channels	Indicator	Target value P2	Achievements April 2024
ECONUTRI website	100,000 websites visits; 200 downloads per public deliverable	300,000 new visits; 2000 new total downloads	Visits: 9,919
e-Newsletter summarising all activities related to the project.	every 6 months, 600 recipients	every 6 months, 1000 new recipients	2 Newsletters, 24 subscribers
Promotional material in digital and hardcopy form (posters, leaflets/flyers).	e-material sent to 1000 recipients	2000 recipients	Project reporting
Videos with project information and interviews	>10,000 YouTube views, 10 videos	>20,000 new YouTube views	5 videos, 95 views
Social media presence with project accounts on Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and Instagram.	>5 posts per month 1,500 followers per project account	1,500 new followers per project account	LinkedIn: 1087 followers Twitter: 106 followers Facebook:111 followers

			Instagram: 91 followers
Project workshops: 3 thematic workshops will be organised.	200 attendees	-	-
Visits to schools: each partner will visit at least one school in its territory.	28 schools	200 schools	3
Promotion through hackathons. A hackathon will be organised to fine-tune nutrient management plans and promote the application of DSS by growers and advisors.	100 participants	>1,000 followers in social media (e.g., YouTube)	-

7 EXPLOITATION PLAN

The exploitation strategy of ECONUTRI relates to the way each project partner individually, and the project partnership, intend to use the project results for scientific, societal, economic purposes, as well as for policy making. The strong industrial participation in ECONUTRI brings strong expertise and benefits for an effective exploitation strategy.

The exploitation strategy covers three key phases, each essential for maximizing the impact of the project results and ensuring successful implementation. While these phases were initially outlined in the first PDEC, they are restated in this updated version of the PDEC (2nd PDEC) in order to underscore their importance within the project framework. It serves as a reminder to all stakeholders of the structured approach needed to effectively exploit the project outcomes. Furthermore, it ensures clarity and continuity for all project stakeholders by being well informed about the approach taken towards exploiting project results. By highlighting these phases again, the project emphasizes its commitment to thorough planning and execution throughout the exploitation process.

P1	<p>Phase 1 – Initial exploitation (during project implementation): Initial exploitation activities will commence with the onset of the ECONUTRI programme, coordinated by CETRI, SPI and AUA. The initial take-up activities will enable technology adaptation and integration, while ECONUTRI systems will be reviewed, optimised, and demonstrated at full scale, thereby mitigating the risk of technology roll-out to competitors. Relationship with potential customers will be established. Possible formation of a joint venture that will take the form of a new distinct legal entity or constitute a business unit within an already existing company.</p>
P1	<p>Phase 2 – Early-stage commercialisation and implementation at Full Scale (for 1 year market roll-out): Early exploitation activities will take place targeting take-up of the innovative systems by early customers (primarily large farmers). Investment for the advanced demonstrated systems is anticipated to be provided directly by the industrial partners. However, external investment will also be considered, if capital finance is not available within the required timeframe. Partners will also</p>

	consider licensing a limited number of private agri-food companies to use novel products, to ensure the appropriate funding for full commercialisation.
P2	<p>Phase 3 – Exploitation within European and Chinese Markets (starting 1 year after the project end): Having validated the implementation and roll-out of the technology with partners, the consortium will commence exploiting the technology across the wider European and Chinese farming markets. Accordingly, discussions that take place with European farmers will then be transformed into contracts. It is anticipated that large and medium farms across Europe will invest directly to pay for the full ECONUTRI systems and services, to benefit from the innovative approach with a fast ROI. Smaller farms will be targeted as well from the 3rd year of exploitation. 5 years after the onset of the commercialisation process, partners will consider licensing more nutrient management companies with the ECONUTRI technology, further increasing the penetration rate of the developed solutions in the market.</p>

As described in the Grant Agreement, after having defined the ownership of each result, partners will explore and define their exploitation plan e.g., patenting, knowledge exploitation, royalties, and market product development. In the updated PDEC, it is noted that the ownership of each project result has not yet been defined due to the ongoing nature of the project and the limited number of concluded results. As a result, the process of defining ownership is still in its initial phase. This means that the project consortium is still working to determine which partner or partners will have ownership rights over specific project results. Until ownership is determined, it's challenging to proceed with the formal exploration and definition of exploitation plans, such as patenting, knowledge exploitation, royalties, and product development.

Despite this early phase, the consortium remains dedicated to identifying opportunities and defining suitable exploitable results as the project advances. While many key exploitable results were presented in the initial plan, they are reintroduced in this second version for consistency, presented in Table 8 below.

Table 6 - ECONUTRI Key Exploitable Results and expected TRLs

	Key Exploitable Results	IPR Owner	TRL
1	Integrated ECONUTRI system to transition to circular bio-based systems in agriculture	All partners	7
2	NUTRISENSE: advanced version available on-line on subscription basis to optimise fertigation	AUA	8
3	Hyperspectral analysis algorithms for estimating nutrient needs	AUA	7
4	Practical System-Function Indicators for Sustainable Cropping: NUE & other ecosystem services	JHI	8
5	OTICE: advanced version available for wide on-farm use	EV ILVO & ATB	8
6	Guides to (i) nutrient recovery from organic rest products, (ii) spreading of pelleted organic fertilizers	NIBIO, UNITO	7
7	Optimised steering software of manure spreaders for optimal manure spreading & emission reduction	Vervaet/ODYC	7
8	VEGYSYST-DSS: an advanced version will be freely available on-line to optimise fertigation solutions	UAL	9
9	VIRTUAL LYSIMETER: advanced DSS for optimal fertigation, on-line available on subscription basis	WUR	8
10	Nutrient supply tailored to crop needs and additives to reduce gaseous emissions in animal farms	ARI	7
11	Innovative technologies reducing GHG and NH ₃ emissions in barns, storages and on fields	WP4 partners	7
12	Protocols and standards for sustainable cascade hydroponics farming, system simulation/validation	UTH	8
13	LCA and model-based simulators of three key innovations that reduce nutrient leaching and GHGs	IGZ, AUA	7
14	Compact robust real-time 8-ion nutrient ion analyser for horticulture. Integrated with NUTRISENSE	CG	9
15	Dissemination of DSS for precision fertigation management using diverse diffusion approaches	UAL, COEXPHAL	8
16	Protocols on use of novel microbiological consortia to accelerate composting of organic rest products	INHORT	7
17	Integrated measures for controlling of black soil degradation and NUE improvement	HAAS	7

18	N stabilizers to enhance NUE and reduce N pollution	CAU, SVG	7
19	Humic acid-based fertilizer reducing fertilizer input and improving fertilizer efficiency	Stanley	7
20	An integrated approach to improve soil fertility and health towards crop production	NAU	7
21	Quantitative recommendation of N and P in organic cropping to reduce N and P content in profile soil	HAAFS	7

Furthermore, based on suggestions from partners, below is a list outlining where exploitation will occur while taking into account IPR issues (mainly covered by the Consortium Agreement), probable additional public and private funding for further TRL development and the preliminary business plan outlined by SPI in the next section.

- **Partnerships:** Collaborating with industry partners to integrate the project's results into existing products or services.
- **Commercialization:** Selling project's technologies or services developed through the project to businesses or consumers.
- **Licensing:** Granting other companies or organizations the right to use the project's intellectual property in exchange for royalties or fees.
- **Spin-offs:** Creating new startup companies based on technologies or innovations developed during the project.
- **Technology transfer:** Transferring knowledge and technology developed in the project to other industries or applications.
- **Policy impact:** Informing and influencing policy decisions based on the project's findings and recommendations.
- **Capacity building:** Training programs or workshops to share expertise and knowledge gained from the project with relevant stakeholders.
- **Open-source dissemination:** Making project results freely available to the public for further development and use.
- **International collaboration:** Partnering with organizations or institutions in other countries, to apply the project's results on a global scale.
- **Education and outreach:** Developing educational materials or outreach programs to raise awareness and disseminate project findings to wider audiences.

7.1 Partner specific exploitation Plans

All partners are highly interested in strengthening their organisations by exploiting the project's end results. In line with the proposal the organizations are divided into 4 groups.

- **Industrial partners** CG, CETRI, METEC, ODYC, Vervaet, WP, Augmenta, SPI, Stanley and SVG intend to grow in their dedicated fields getting benefitted by the new business opportunities the exploitation of the project innovations will create.
- **Research partners** AUA, UAL, UTH, IGZ, JHI, WUR, NIBIO, UNITO, UTAD, ATB, EV ILVO, HAAS, NAU, CAU and HAAFS will be strengthened by actions, such as promotion of their novel technologies to the private sector for commercial exploitation, joint publications, student and staff exchanges, participation in workshops and training courses, and presentation at meetings, as well as making sure that their research is applied in the most efficient way.
- **Public and non-profit partners** ARI, ESSRG, COEXPHAL and LGNL will have the opportunity to transfer generated forefront knowledge to their regions / members.

Several research partners have provided a preliminary exploitation plan in the first PDEC, and is also included in this update, in Table 9 below to emphasize their continued relevance within the project framework.

A notable addition to this section is the establishment of a spinoff company by the Agricultural University of Athens (AUA) team of ECONUTRI, named “NUTRISENSE - Nature-based Solutions for Nutrient Management in Agriculture P.C.”, shortly referenced as “NUTRISENSE PC”. The aim of NUTRISENSE PC (NUTRISENSE I.K.E. in Greek) is to exploit the research findings originating from ECONUTRI and some older research projects feeding into ECONUTRI (NUTRISENSE and VEG-ADAPT), thus increasing their TRL from 5 to 8. The core technology exploited by the spinoff company is the DSS NUTRISENSE in its two versions, namely SOIL NutriSense and SOILLESS NutriSense, which are deployed by ECONUTRI as innovative technologies in T3.2 and T3.3, respectively. The DSS NUTRISENSE is available both in Greek and English and thus it is accessible and commercially available to all growers internationally. The ECONUTRI team plans to translate the **DSS NUTRISENSE** into multiple languages, starting with Chinese. Thus, making agricultural knowledge accessible and user-friendly for non-English speakers, empowering growers and agronomists. The link to the webpage of NUTRISENSE PC is: <https://nutrisense.online>.

Table 7 - Partner Primary Exploitation plan

Partner Name	Agricultural University of Athens (AUA) P1
Content to be exploited	Web-accessible Decision Support System (DSS) NUTRISENSE
Approach towards Exploitation	NUTRISENSE, as a DSS supporting vegetable producing growers (both in soil-grown and soilless cropping systems) is already commercially exploited through the spinoff company NUTRISENSE PC, which was founded by the AUA team of ECONUTRI in January 2024. The DSS NUTRISENSE is on-line available on a subscription basis through the link https://nutrisense.online/ . The AUA team has further developed and optimized the functionality of the NUTRISENSE DSS by establishing two alternative versions, one for soil-grown crops and another one for soilless growers (SOIL NUTRISENSE & SOILLESS NUTRISENSE). Furthermore, the AUA team has developed a special version within SOILLESS NUTRISENSE for growers who wish to use the technology of ion selective electrodes (ISEs) to optimize nutrient recycling in closed-loop soilless cultivation systems. The upgraded NUTRISENSE is currently fully commercialized as it is offered by NUTRISENSE PC as a full package of services for sustainable nutrient management in open-field and greenhouse vegetable crops on subscription basis.
Spin-off launched	
Partner Name	University of Thessaly (UTH) P3
Content to be exploited	DSS for water and nutrient management simulation in a cascade cropping system
Approach towards Exploitation	The DSS will be used to simulate the water and nutrient inputs and outputs in a cascade system where the drainages of a donor crop (cucumbers) will be fully used to meet the nutritional needs of a secondary crop (melons). UTH, as a research partner, will proceed to joint publications based on the efficiency of this prediction model as well as to training courses to further exploit the obtained results
Partner Name	Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research (NIBIO) P7
Content to be exploited	Nutrient calibration is necessary in order to valorize materials derived from biowaste processing.
Approach towards Exploitation	Biowastes contain valuable nutrients, that will imply economic losses if not recovered. Moreover, if the nutrients are spread to the environment, nature values can be damaged or even destroyed. Therefore, the recovery of the nutrients and transformation of wastes into valuable products will be important for the economy and the environment. We aim at extracting phosphorus (struvite precipitation) and nitrogen (NH ₄ – stripping) from the waste streams, for more economic and environmental sound

	uses. Our work will be to optimize and demonstrate these technologies on lab scale to prepare for industrialization of the processes. Enriching biowaste-based fertilizer products may be important to upgrade the fertilizers and improve their ability to compete with mineral fertilizers. The knowledge and technology developed will be disseminated/demonstrated to encourage widespread adaptation.
Partner Name	Agricultural Research Institute (ARI) P8
Content to be exploited	Policy making
Approach towards Exploitation	The ECONUTRI technology will be disseminated in Cyprus, to the Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment, for policy making decisions. The results will be used for the creation of a handbook that will be distributed to the farmers.
Partner Name	Leibniz Institute of Agricultural Engineering and Bioeconomy (ATB) P16
Content to be exploited	Urease inhibitor to reduce emissions from dairy barns. Effect of fast manure removal by using cleaning robots and manure scrapers on emissions from dairy barns.
Approach towards Exploitation	ATB will evaluate the effect of urease inhibitors and manure-cleaning robots at real scale as both of these techniques possibly reduce the emission of GHGs and NH ₃ up to 20% from dairy barns. After the successful evaluation, ATB will promote the adoption/utilization/sale of urease inhibitors and cleaning robots at large scale to increase the overall mitigation of gaseous emissions from livestock production systems.
Partner Name	Institute for Agricultural and Food Research (EV ILVO) P21
Content to be exploited	ILVO will evaluate the effect of fast manure removal in a fattening pig barn as this technique possibly reduces the emission of GHGs and NH ₃ . ILVO will also evaluate the functionality of an online emission monitoring system (OTICE) in pilot trials.
Approach towards Exploitation	After the successful evaluation, ILVO will promote the application of fast manure removal at large scale to increase the overall mitigation of gaseous emissions from livestock production systems. Furthermore, ILVO will promote the application of an online emission monitoring system at large scale, since it can contribute to very useful insights in the emissions of barns and could result in adaptation of the farmers management to reduce the gaseous emissions from their barns
Partner Name	James Hutton Institute (JHI) P30
Content to be exploited	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. "Innovation Stacking" of agronomic approaches in a long-term experimental integrated platform - the Centre for Sustainable Cropping (CSC). The stacked approaches themselves are worth reporting. 2. LCA of the CSC platform (attributorial and consequential LCA). LCA impact assessment can be linked to ESs indicators. So, system function as well as impact can be evaluated. This linking of LCA to ES is also a technology development. 3. LCA data to inform development of GOBLIN -model - to generate "Crop-GOBLIN" for identification of best scenarios for upscaling of integrated farming approach. 4. Data and insights from the WP3 on "legume-legume" crop mixtures trial can: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) provide an informative narrative to limit synthetic fertiliser N use; and b) data will feed into LCA, development of crop-GOBLIN, and so assess crop-mixture based solutions in the "which cropped system/rotation" scenario analysis.
Approach towards Exploitation	1. collect and assess data, methods development, peer-reviewed publications necessary as evidence base.

	<p>2. in parallel with the above make initial key-data findings known to key industry stakeholders/sponsors.</p> <p>3. showcase findings at key stakeholder events: Arable Scotland, Royal Highland Show, Hannah Dairy Research Foundation (annual meeting), international research conferences (International Legume Society).</p> <p>4. LCA approach, and crop-GOBLIN model made openly available and Open Access resource.</p> <p>5. build integrated farm network around the CSC platform.</p>
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Additional information is provided by the partners through an IPR registry table presented below, where detailed exploitation plans are described.

UAL (P2) IPR REGISTRY

Results Information					Results' Ownership and IPR Strategy					Technology Readiness Level (TRL)
No	Title	Description	Relation to the work structure	Relevant Background Knowledge & IP	Beneficiary Name	Shares of IP rights (%)	Nature of Involvement	Preferred protection route	ECONUTRI Result belongs to	Expected TRL at project end
			Relevant Task(s) / Relevant Deliverable(s)					Preferred exploitation route	Products or Services that incorporate this result/data/tool	
1	VEGSYST-DSS: an advanced version will be freely available on-line to optimise fertigation solutions		WP3	Work in previous projects, all published	UAL	100%	Author of the VEGSYST DSS	No protection	Public	9
			Task 3.2 Innovative models/ technologies to control N/P emissions from soil-grown vegetable crops D3.1. A sustainable nutrient management plan for conventional and							

			organic agriculture to improve NUE and minimise nitrate and phosphorus emissions to water bodies (M24, M42). D3.2. Guidelines and suitable DSSs for recycling and facilitating multi-use of fertigation effluents in soilless crops (M36).							
2	Dissemination of DSS for precision fertigation management using diverse diffusion approaches	Based on field demonstrations, experiences with the fertigation protocols developed by the UAL, will be made known to the horticultural sector in Almería	<p>WP3</p> <p>Task 3.2 Innovative models/ technologies to control N/P emissions from soil-grown vegetable crops (M1 – M42);</p> <p>D3.1. A sustainable nutrient management plan for conventional and organic agriculture to improve NUE and minimise nitrate and phosphorus emissions to water bodies (M24, M42).</p>	Published information on UAL	UAL	50%	investigator	No protection	Public	9

			D3.2. Guidelines and suitable DSSs for recycling and facilitating multi-use of fertigation effluents in soilless crops (M36).							
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IGZ (P4) IPR REGISTRY

Results Information					Results' Ownership and IPR Strategy					Technology Readiness Level (TRL)
No	Title	Description	Relation to the work structure	Relevant Background Knowledge & IP	Beneficiary Name	Share of IP rights (%)	Nature of Involvement	Preferred protection route	ECONUTRI Result belongs to	Expected TRL at project end
			Relevant Task(s) / Relevant Deliverable(s)					Preferred exploitation route	Products or Services that incorporate this Result	
1	Model-based simulator of innovations 2 (Technologies for nutrient recovery and safe land application of raw waste materials)	Process-based models coded in Matlab for simulation studies of Innovation 2 (UNITO, NIBIO)	Dissemination activity WP2/WP5 / Deliverable D1.1, D1.2; D5.1	Knowledge on innovation 2 with biogas-waste stream circles and systems design technology (Matlab codes etc.)	IGZ	50%	Investigator	Open Source Licensing 1) Collaborative Research 2) Consultancy and Services 3) Standards Contribution	IGZ	7

2	Model-based simulator of innovation 14 (Cascade soilless system to reuse the effluents in a sequence of crops)	Process-based models coded in Matlab for simulation studies of Innovation 14 (UTH)		Knowledge on innovation 13 with Cascade Hydroponics systems design technology (Matlab codes etc.)	IGZ	50%	Investigator	Open Source Licensing	IGZ	7
								1) Collaborative Research 2) Consultancy and Services 3) Standards Contribution		
3	Model-based simulator of innovation 13 (Real-time sensing with ISEs to maximise nutrient recycling in soilless cropping)	Process-based models coded in Matlab for simulation studies of Innovation 13 (AUA)		Knowledge on innovation 14 with nutrient selective monitoring and dosing; systems design technology (Matlab codes etc.)	IGZ	50%	Investigator	Open Source Licensing	IGZ	7
								1) Collaborative Research 2) Consultancy and Services 3) Standards Contribution		
4	Model-based simulator of innovation 21 (Reducing GHG emissions from soil grown crops through additives to fertilizers)	Process-based models coded in Matlab for simulation studies of Innovation 21 (INHORT)		Systems design technology (Matlab codes etc.)	IGZ	50%	Investigator	Open Source Licensing	IGZ	6
								1) Collaborative Research 2) Consultancy and Services 3) Standards Contribution		

ARI (P8) IPR REGISTRY

Results Information					Results' Ownership and IPR Strategy					Technology Readiness Level (TRL)
No	Title	Description	Relation to the work structure	Relevant Background Knowledge & IP	Beneficiary Name	Shares of IP rights (%)	Nature of Involvement	Preferred protection route	ECONUTRI Result belongs to	Expected TRL at project end
			Relevant Task(s) / Relevant Deliverable(s)					Preferred exploitation route	Products or Services that incorporate this Result	
1	The exploitation of co-composting green waste with digestate or hydroponic waste	Educational sessions and training for students. Informative sessions to help others implement and benefit from proposed technology <i>(Nicosia, Cyprus 16/04/2024)</i>	Dissemination activity / Education -Training	Innovative technologies reducing nutrient pollution from manure and other organic matrices	ARI	N/A	Knowledge transfer / Providing expertise / Education -Training	Open-Source Licensing	ARI	7
			WP2 (Task 2.1) / School visit / Deliverable D1.2					Collaborative Research / Consultancy and Services / Standards Contribution	Partnering with stakeholders or other companies / Sharing of findings and providing expertise and services related to the technology.	
2	Agri-environmental sensing equipment in potato cropping systems in Cyprus to control fertilization and	Training and informative sessions for students and presentation of results and share findings at events for interested parties. <i>(Nicosia, 06/07/2023; Tochni, Cyprus 03/04/2024; Xylo tympou, Cyprus,</i>	Dissemination activity / Education -Training	Sustainable nutrient and water management / climate change adaptation strategies	ARI	N/A	Knowledge transfer / Providing expertise / Education -Training	Open Source Licensing	ARI	8
			WP3 (Task 3.1) / Deliverable					Collaborative Research / Consultancy	Partnering with other companies or organizations	

	irrigation and minimize nutrient (N, P)	10/04/2024;Nicosia, Cyprus, 16/04/2024, see deliverables report)	e D1.1, D1.2	in field crops.				ncy and Services / Standards Contribution	ons to jointly develop and commercialize the technology / Sharing of findings and providing expertise and related to the technology.	
3	Partial substitution of nitrate (NO ₃ ⁻) with chloride (Cl ⁻) in hydroponics, allows for complete recycling of the nutrient solution and lower N inputs and losses	Training and informative sessions for students and presentation of results and share findings at events for interested parties. (Nicosia, 06/07/2023;Tochni, Cyprus 03/04/2024;Xylotymbo u, Cyprus, 10/04/2024;Nicosia, Cyprus, 16/04/2024, see deliverables report)	Dissemination activity	Sustainable nutrient and water management / climate change adaptation strategies in protected crops.	ARI	N/A	Knowledge transfer / Providing expertise / Education-Training	Open Source Licensing	ARI	7
			WP3 (Task 3.3) / Deliverable D1.1, D1.2					Collaborative Research / Consultancy and Services / Standards Contribution	Partnering with other interested parties to jointly develop the technology / Sharing of findings and providing expertise and related to the technology.	
4	The effect of additives (e.g. biochar) on CO ₂ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O and NH ₃ emissions in animal farms	Training and informative sessions, and presentation of research at field events. (Nicosia, Cyprus, 16/04/2024 and 26/04/20, see deliverables report)	Dissemination activity	Emission reduction technologies for animal farms	ARI	N/A	Presentation, dissemination / Knowledge transfer / Develop new applications	Open Source Licensing	ARI	7
			WP4 (Task 4.1 and Task 4.2) / Deliverable D1.2					Collaborative Research / Consultancy and Services / Standards Contribution	Sharing of findings and providing expertise and services related to the technology for the emission reduction in animal farms.	

UNITO (P10) IPR REGISTRY

Results Information					Results' Ownership and IPR Strategy					Technology Readiness Level (TRL)
No	Title	Description	Relation to the work structure	Relevant Background Knowledge & IP	Beneficiary Name	Shares of IP rights (%)	Nature of Involvement	Preferred protection route	ECONUTRI Result belongs to	Expected TRL at project end
			Relevant Task(s) / Relevant Deliverable(s)					Preferred exploitation route	Products or Services that incorporate this Result	
3	Smoke water as a biostimulant	Treatment with smoke water or one of its bioactive ingredients (karrikins) to improve NUE in tomato	WP3	Not applicable	UNITO	Not applicable	Academic institution	No IP protection	Public Results	4
			Task 3.4 Deliverable 3.1					Collaborative Research	There are several publications suggesting this application, but protocols need to be fine-tuned to the crop. Then, it could be incorporated into biostimulants	

COEXPHAL (P12) IPR REGISTRY

Results Information					Results' Ownership and IPR Strategy					Technology Readiness Level (TRL)
No	Title	Description	Relation to the work structure	Relevant Background Knowledge & IP	Beneficiary Name	Share of IP rights (%)	Nature of Involvement	Preferred protection route	ECONUTRI Result belongs to	Expected TRL at project end
			Relevant Task(s) / Relevant Deliverable(s)					Preferred exploitation route	Products or Services that incorporate this Result	
1	Dissemination of DSS for precision fertigation management using diverse diffusion approaches	Based on field demonstrations, experiences with the fertigation protocols developed by the UAL, will be made known to the horticultural sector in Almería	<p>WP3</p> <p>Task 3.2 Innovative models/ technologies to control N/P emissions from soil-grown vegetable crops (M1 – M42); D3.1. A sustainable nutrient management plan for conventional and organic agriculture to improve NUE and minimise nitrate and phosphorus emissions to water bodies (M24, M42).</p> <p>D3.2. Guidelines and suitable DSSs for recycling and</p>	Published information UAL	COEXPHAL	50%	investigator	<p>No protection</p> <p>Public</p>	Public	9

			facilitating multi-use of fertigation effluents in soilless crops (M36).							
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ODYC & VERVAET (P14 &P15) IPR REGISTRY

Results Information					Results' Ownership and IPR Strategy					Technology Readiness Level (TRL)
No	Title	Description	Relation to the work structure	Relevant Background Knowledge & IP	Beneficiary Name	Share of IP rights (%)	Nature of Involvement	Preferred protection route	ECONUTRI Result belongs to	Expected TRL at project end
			Relevant Task(s) / Relevant Deliverable(s)					Preferred exploitation route	Products or Services that incorporate this Result	
1	NPK NIR data in VERVAET CONNECT	Direct Integration on NPK NIR sensor data on Vervaeet machinery (access to data on the Vervaeet machinery)	WP3 & WP4	Manure machinima NPK sensor integration	Vervaeet	100%	ODYC involvement in support on the development	Trade Secrets	Vervaeet	TRL 8
			T3.1 & T4.3					Commercialisation	Vervaeet Connect portfolio	

INHORT (P18) IPR REGISTRY

Results Information					Results' Ownership and IPR Strategy					Technology Readiness Level (TRL)
No	Title	Description	Relation to the work structure	Relevant Background Knowledge & IP	Beneficiary Name	Share of IP rights (%)	Nature of Involvement	Preferred protection route	ECONUTRI Result belongs to	Expected TRL at project end
			Relevant Task(s) / Relevant Deliverable(s)					Preferred exploitation route	Products or Services that incorporate this Result	
1	Collaborative Research	Cooperation with research institutions or other companies to further develop technology for producing microbial consortia.	WP2	Multiplication and assembly of beneficial microorganisms into consortia.	1. INHORT holds the IPRs	INHORT 100%	INHORT is involved in the development and delivery of consortia of beneficial microorganisms to other scientific partners for further validation and implementation.	Collaborative research and licensing of newly developed microbial consortia.	INHORT	TRL 7
			Task 2.1					1. Collaborative research with research institutions.		
2	Collaborative Research	Cooperation with research institutions, companies producing	WP2	Development and production of composts enriched with	1. INHORT holds the IPRs	INHORT 100%	INHORT is involved in the development and delivery of	Joint research on newly developed composts.	INHORT	TRL 7

		biofertilizers and agricultural advisors to further develop technologies for producing composts containing consortia of beneficial microorganisms.	Task 2.1.3	beneficial soil microorganisms.	2. companies producing composts on an industrial scale		composts to other scientific partners of the project for further implementation of tasks.	<p>Joint research</p> <p>1. Cooperation with research institutions or other companies.</p> <p>2. Joint research projects and co-creation of new applications of the developed consortia of beneficial microorganisms.</p>	Development of composts that have a beneficial effect on plants and reduce greenhouse gas emissions.	
3	Consultancy and Services	Providing knowledge and services related to the technology of developing microbial consortia.	WP1	knowledge in conducting training workshops regarding the promotion and commercialization of developed products containing microbial consortia and useful substances.	<p>1. INHORT owns the IPRs.</p> <p>2. Producers of biofertilizers and composts.</p> <p>3. Producers of vegetables and fruits.</p>	INHORT 100%	INHORT is involved in conducting training workshops			TRL 7
			Task 1.2						Consultancy and services	

4	Consultancy and Services	Providing knowledge and services related to the technology of developing composts enriched with consortia of beneficial microorganisms	WP1	knowledge in conducting training workshops.	1. INHORT owns the IPRs 2. Producers of biofertilizers and composts, 3. Producers of vegetables and fruit.	INHORT 100%	INHORT is involved in conducting training workshops and participating in conferences			TRL7
			Task 1.2							

EV ILVO (P21) IPR REGISTRY

Results Information					Results' Ownership and IPR Strategy					Technology Readiness Level (TRL)
No	Title	Description	Relation to the work structure	Relevant Background Knowledge & IP	Beneficiary Name	Shares of IP rights (%)	Nature of Involvement	Preferred protection route	ECONUTRI Result belongs to	Expected TRL at project end
			Relevant Task(s) / Relevant					Preferred exploitation route	Products or Services that incorporat	

			Deliverable(s)						Result	
1	OTICE	Emission monitoring system	WP 4	OTICE was started in the Milkey project, no IP rights	EV ILVO	Not applicable	Research institute	Open Source Licensing	Public results	8
			Task 4.4 / Deliverable 4.1					Collaborative Research and Standards Contribution	2	
2	Frequent manure removal	Management action that can be performed in barns to remove manure from the barn on a frequent basis in order to reduce emissions	WP 4	Not applicable	EV ILVO	Not applicable	Research institute	No IP protection	Public results	9
			Task 4.1 / Deliverable 4.1					Collaborative Research	There are already several existing systems that perform frequent manure removal in pig and dairy barns	

STANLEY (P24) IPR REGISTRY

Results Information					Results' Ownership and IPR Strategy					Technology Readiness Level (TRL)
No	Title	Description	Relation to the work structure	Relevant Background Knowledge & IP	Beneficiary Name	Shares of IP rights (%)	Nature of Involvement	Preferred protection route	ECONUTRI Result belongs to	Expected TRL at project end
			Relevant Task(s) / Relevant Deliverable(s)					Preferred exploitation route	Products or Services that incorporate this Result	

1	Humic acid - based fertilizer reduces fertilizer input and increases NUE	Selecting high-quality humic acid mineral and uses physical and chemical methods for activation to obtain activated humic acid containing more carboxylic groups and phenolic hydroxyl groups, which is riched in fulvic acid and has a higher biological activity and widely application with less dosage . Adding it to the fertilizer to get humic acid fertilizer, which can significantly promote roots growth and increase nutrients absorption in crops.	WP3	Humic acid fertilizer can promote roots growth and increase nutrients absorption in crops.	Stanley	100	A development	Trademark	Stanley	7
		Task (3.4)						Promoting the application of humic acid fertilizer through the sales channels	Providing expertise and services related to the humic acid fertilizer	

SVG (P25) IPR REGISTRY

Results Information					Results' Ownership and IPR Strategy					Technology Readiness Level (TRL)
No	Title	Description	Relation to the work structure	Relevant Background Knowledge & IP	Beneficiary Name	Shares of IP rights (%)	Nature of Involvement	Preferred protection route	ECONUTRI Result belongs to	Expected TRL at project end
			Relevant Task(s) / Relevant Deliverable(s)					Preferred exploitation route	Products or Services that incorporate this Result	
1	Promote the use of DSS devices to reduce NO3-leaching	In greenhouse vegetable cropping system, an integrated nutrient management for precision fertigation management to maximise use of nutrients in soil will be recommended, and the fertigation protocols will be developed.	WP3	Innovative technologies reducing nitrogen and phosphorus pollution in greenhouse vegetable system	SVG	N/A	Presentation and dissemination	No protection	Public	7
			Task 3.2 Innovative models/technologies to control N/P emissions from soil-grown vegetable crops (M1 – M42)/ Deliverable D1.2					Core demonstration zone demonstration	Fertigation protocols	

JHI (P30) IPR REGISTRY

Results Information					Results' Ownership and IPR Strategy					Technology Readiness Level (TRL)
No	Title	Description	Relation to the work structure	Relevant Background Knowledge & IP	Beneficiary Name	Shares of IP rights (%)	Nature of Involvement	Preferred protection route	ECONUTRI Result belongs to	Expected TRL at project end
			Relevant Task(s) / Relevant Deliverable(s)					Preferred exploitation route	Products or Services that incorporate this result/data/tool	
1	Long term data from stacked/integrates NbSs	Data from long term integrated cropped system experiment – the Centre for Sustainable Cropping	WP6	long term ecosystem effects (not seen with short term trials)	JHI	N/A	RTO	Open Access data provision (on request)	Publicly available data (on request)	8
			Task 2 and Task 3					Collaborative Research	n/a	
2	Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of legume-led crop sequences (rotations)	LCA data and tools to assess impacts of grain legume cropping; and on subsequent (non-legume) crop production. Includes methods to integrate ecosystem service (i.e., functional) benefits (ESB) assessment to LCA impact	WP6	Frameworks for legume-cropping impact- and ecosystem functional - assessments via LCA+ESB	JHI	N/A	RTO	Open Access data / tools	Publicly available data / tools	8
			Task 2 and Task 3					Collaborative Research	Publicly available data / tools	

		assessment.								
3	Development of "CropGOBLIN"	Land use impact risk assessment for regional scale to assess best uptake options for legume-based cropped systems	WP6	Novel scenario generation tool to identify best cropped system (rotation) options to minimize specific risks (E.g., climate change, terrestrial and mineral pollution etc) – to inform land use decision makers of desired land-use options.	JHI	N/A	RTO	Open Access data / tools	Publicly available data / tools	8
			Task 2 Task 3					Collaborative Research	Publicly available data / tools	
4	NbSs for 'climate change resilience', and optimization of protein yields.	Minimising inputs whilst optimising protein yield using novel legume-based pulse crop mixtures.	WP3	Use of pulse-pulse mixtures for multiple ESBs across the ecosystem and value chain.	JHI	N/A	RTO	Open Access data	Publicly available data / results	6
			Task 3.1					Collaborative Research	Publicly available data / tools	

AUA (P1)

AUA will be a beneficiary for the DSS NUTRISENSE. The beneficiaries of DSS created by other partners of ECONUTRI (e.g. the VegSys by UAL and the Virtual Lysimeter by WUR) will be the respective partners who have created these DSS. More details on these results in the final PDEC.

The intellectual Property Rights of NUTRISENSE belong solely to AUA, as AUA is the sole creator of this DSS. However, other partners and specifically WONDERPLANT and ARI are also using NUTRISENSE free of charge during the project life and thus they also benefit from this DSS. Furthermore, a substantial number of stakeholders (>10) are currently benefiting from NUTRISENSE as they make use of this DSS free of charge in pilot studies and tests.

7.2 Econutri Business Plan

7.2.1 Introduction

The ECONUTRI project, funded by Horizon Europe, is dedicated to tackling pressing environmental challenges in agriculture through advanced nutrient management technologies. Focused on reducing nitrogen and phosphorus pollution, ECONUTRI aligns with the EU's Green Deal goals, aiming to provide sustainable solutions for the agricultural sectors in Europe and China. This business plan outlines a strategic roadmap for advancing ECONUTRI's 24 cutting-edge technologies from their current development stages to full market readiness. By integrating detailed market analysis, strategic marketing and sales strategies, and comprehensive financial planning, the plan ensures that ECONUTRI's innovations deliver practical benefits to farmers and comply with regulatory standards. Ultimately, this plan serves as a guide for the successful commercialisation of ECONUTRI's technologies, fostering a more sustainable agricultural future.

7.2.2 Methodology for Business Plan Development

The business plan for the ECONUTRI project is developed with the aim of guiding the commercialisation of innovative agricultural technologies that align with the EU's environmental objectives under Horizon Europe. This plan articulates the strategic approach to transitioning these technologies from their current development stages to market readiness, ensuring they effectively address the key challenges in nutrient management within agriculture.

The methodology underpinning the ECONUTRI Business Model Canvas offers a structured framework that connects with various components of the canvas to ensure a coherent strategy for bringing innovative agricultural technologies to market. The process begins with a detailed analysis of market needs and operational planning, directly informing the "Customer Segments" and "Value Proposition" sections of the canvas. This ensures that our technologies are tailored to meet the needs of our target markets and deliver exceptional value. Additionally, a structured approach to stakeholder and partner engagement enhances the "Partners + Key Stakeholders" component, fostering fruitful collaborations that align with both developmental and commercialisation goals.

Market Analysis: A thorough market analysis forms the core of the business plan. This analysis focuses on understanding the target markets in Europe and China, identifying key demographic, geographic, and economic factors that influence agricultural practices and technology adoption. According to Eurostat, there are 10.5 million agricultural holdings in the EU, with two-thirds less than 5 hectares in size. This presents a substantial market opportunity for ECONUTRI, especially as it offers a holistic solution that no other agri-food company currently provides. The market demand for nutrient management solutions is projected to rise rapidly. Competitors include major companies such as Ceres Imaging, Innosense LLC, CCM EResearch Limited, environmental monitoring, and others, highlighting the significant gap ECONUTRI is poised to fill.

Product Strategy: The product strategy section describes each of the 24 technologies, outlining their functionalities, current development status, and anticipated capabilities upon reaching TRL 7-8. The value propositions are clearly articulated, emphasising the benefits such as enhanced efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and significant environmental impacts compared to existing solutions. ECONUTRI's product strategy focuses on delivering state-of-the-art technologies that optimise nutrient management in agriculture. The project's key exploitable results (KERs) are crucial to this strategy, each offering significant advancements and competitive advantages. Each KER will be detailed in the business plan, including market potential, application scenarios, and competitive advantages.

Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

- **NUTRISENSE:** An advanced decision support system (DSS) that provides actionable insights for precision agriculture, improving nutrient management and reducing waste.
- **VEGSYST-DSS:** A sophisticated DSS for fertigation and nutrient management, offering significant improvements in efficiency and environmental impact.
- **Integrated Circular Bio-Based Systems:** Technologies designed to create sustainable nutrient loops within agricultural systems.
- **Advanced Nutrient Monitoring Technologies:** Tools that provide real-time data on soil and plant nutrient levels to optimise fertilizer use.
- **Simulation Models for Cascade Cropping Systems:** Data-driven models to enhance decision-making in multi-crop systems, improving resource efficiency.

Marketing and Sales Strategy: The marketing and sales strategies are designed to effectively communicate the benefits of the ECONUTRI technologies to the identified customer segments. This includes a mix of digital marketing, direct participation in industry conferences, and educational workshops aimed at raising awareness and fostering adoption. Sales strategies are defined to include both direct sales and partnerships with agricultural equipment and service providers, supported by a competitive pricing model that reflects the value offered to different market segments.

Financial Projections and Funding: The financial section projects the revenue streams from technology sales, licensing agreements, and potential subscription services. It also identifies the funding requirements necessary to achieve these projections and explores potential sources of investment beyond the initial Horizon Europe grant.

Governance and Compliance: This section outlines strategies for managing intellectual property rights and ensuring compliance with international regulatory standards. It highlights the importance of establishing clear guidelines for intellectual property management to protect and leverage the project's innovations.

Risk Management: Risk management is crucial to the plan, identifying potential risks related to technology adoption, market acceptance, and operational execution. The business plan includes detailed contingency strategies to mitigate these risks, ensuring the project's sustainability and success.

Stakeholder Engagement: The plan emphasises the importance of continuous engagement with all stakeholders, including partners, potential customers, and regulatory bodies. Regular communication and feedback mechanisms are established to ensure that all stakeholders are informed and involved in the project's progress.

Review and Iteration: Finally, the business plan is treated as a dynamic document, subject to regular reviews and updates based on project progress, market dynamics, and stakeholder feedback. This iterative process ensures that the plan remains relevant and effective throughout the project lifecycle.

7.2.3 Strategic Approach to Commercialisation, Scaling, and Intellectual Property Management

To ensure ECONUTRI's business plan is effective and aligns with its strategic direction, it's essential to integrate detailed information on Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) from various partners. Each partner's unique contributions shape ECONUTRI's value proposition and market approach.

For example, ARI has developed co-composting systems and agri-environmental sensing equipment under open-source licenses. This impacts the business model by defining technology readiness levels (TRL), intellectual property management, and protection routes. Similarly, INHORT's microbial consortia (TRL 7) and UAL's precision fertigation management DSS (TRL 9) offer advanced solutions for nutrient management and sustainable agriculture, which refine the business model's value propositions.

Incorporating these details involves leveraging specific IPR strategies and experimental outcomes to shape the commercialisation strategy. Understanding each partner's IPR strategy—whether it involves open-source licensing or trade secrets—helps in structuring licensing agreements and collaborations.

ECONUTRI's strategic plan aims to transition its innovative technologies from development to commercial success by focusing on effective market entry and scaling. The plan includes a detailed approach to commercialisation and IPR management to protect and leverage these innovations. This strategy ensures optimal utilisation of technological advancements and supports a successful market entry and widespread application of ECONUTRI's solutions.

Commercialisation and Upscaling Actions:

Market entry strategy: ECONUTRI will utilise a mix of direct sales and partnerships with agricultural equipment and service providers to enter target markets. The marketing strategy will involve digital marketing, participation in industry conferences, and educational workshops to raise awareness and foster adoption.

Scaling up: partners will leverage their industry connections to scale up technologies. This includes integrating ECONUTRI's solutions with existing agricultural equipment and services and exploring licensing agreements.

Commercial partnerships: forming strategic partnerships with technology providers and regulatory experts to ensure technologies meet international standards and regulations.

Pilot testing: initial deployment of ECONUTRI solutions on farms linked to the project to demonstrate benefits and collect data for broader market applications.

Investment seeking: identifying and securing additional funding sources beyond the Horizon Europe grant to support commercialisation and upscaling efforts.

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Strategy:

- **Intellectual property strategy:** the business plan will detail strategies for managing intellectual property rights, including patenting innovations resulting from the project.
- **Specific technologies and patents:**
 - **Nutrisense:** undergoing patent application to protect the innovative algorithms and decision support system framework.
 - **Vegsys-dss:** patent pending for the unique fertigation and nutrient management modules.
 - **Integrated circular bio-based systems:** patents will be filed for technologies developed to create sustainable nutrient loops.
 - **Advanced nutrient monitoring technologies:** patent applications will cover real-time monitoring tools and methods.

- **Simulation models for cascade cropping systems:** the data-driven models will be patented for their innovative approach to resource efficiency in multi-crop systems.
- **Open-source licensing:** some technologies, such as co-composting systems developed by partner ari, may be protected under open-source licenses to promote broader use and development.

7.2.4 Key Partnerships

Strategic Partnerships play a crucial role in the commercialisation and scaling of ECONUTRI technologies. Each partner contributes to different facets of the business plan:

- **Agricultural University of Athens:** Responsible for the launch and global distribution of NUTRISENSE PC, enhancing the technology's reach and impact in optimising nutrient management.
- **University of Thessaly:** Focuses on developing simulation models for cascade cropping systems, contributing valuable data-driven insights and decision-making tools for sustainable agriculture.
- **Additional Partners:**
 - **Industry Collaborators:** Engaged in joint ventures to integrate ECONUTRI technologies with existing agricultural equipment and services.
 - **Technology Providers:** Offering complementary technologies and expertise to enhance the functionality and adoption of ECONUTRI's solutions.
 - **Regulatory and Compliance Experts:** Ensuring that all technologies adhere to international standards and regulations, facilitating smoother market entry and acceptance.

These partnerships are critical for leveraging resources, accessing new markets, and enhancing the technological and commercial viability of ECONUTRI's offerings.

7.2.5 ECONUTRI Business Model Canvas

The ECONUTRI Business Model Canvas outlines a strategic framework for the commercialisation and deployment of advanced agricultural technologies funded by Horizon Europe. It provides a comprehensive plan for advancing these technologies from development to widespread market adoption.

The development of the canvas is guided by a structured methodology that aligns each element of the business plan—market analysis, partnerships, financial planning, and risk management—with the project's goals. This methodology translates theoretical concepts into actionable strategies.

The process begins with a thorough analysis of market needs, which informs the "Customer Segments" and "Value Proposition" sections of the canvas. This ensures that the technologies are designed to meet specific market demands and deliver significant value. A structured approach to stakeholder and partner engagement enhances the "Partners + Key Stakeholders" section, fostering collaborations essential for both development and commercialisation.

Financial planning is a critical component, leveraging initial funding from Horizon Europe and seeking additional investments to scale the technologies. Regulatory compliance and sustainability practices are integrated into every stage of development, reinforcing the "Social & Environmental Costs" and "Benefits" sections. This ensures that the technologies adhere to international standards and contribute positively to environmental health.

The methodology also addresses risk management by focusing on the effective handling of risks and assets, which supports the "Asset Ownership" and "Cost Structure" components of the canvas. Additionally, it develops strategies for revenue streams and reinvestment, ensuring financial stability and supporting the "Revenue Streams" and "Surplus" sections.

Overall, the ECONUTRI Business Model Canvas, underpinned by this methodology, establishes a robust foundation for the successful implementation and commercialisation of the project’s technologies. It addresses pressing environmental challenges and supports sustainable agricultural practices, aligning with the EU Green Deal’s goals to reduce fertilizer use and nutrient losses by 2030, while enhancing agricultural productivity in Europe and China.

Table 8 - Econutri Business Model Canvas

8 CONCLUSION

The deliverable D1.2 – second release of the Econutri Plan for the dissemination, exploitation and communication, provides the framework and the roadmap that will help the whole consortium to implement the dissemination project results and communication activities.

The aim of the first PDEC was to setup an initial plan at an early stage of the project in order to coordinate in an efficient way the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities that have been agreed in the Grant Agreement of ECONUTRI.

In this second PDEC, the communication and dissemination activities, along with the presented business plan, aim to increase further the awareness of the project's innovative character among stakeholders and the general public. This becomes particularly crucial as the impacts of climate change continue to resonate throughout the food industry. Given the urgency for innovative, sustainable solutions, especially within the agricultural sector, these efforts are essential.

ECONUTRI partners will be accountable for communicating project outcomes via ECONUTRI social media platforms and their individual networks, while AUA and CETRI will oversee the utilization of online tools and channels to ensure broad exposure at the highest level.

ANNEX 1

*eco***nutri**

<https://econutri-project.eu/>